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Sustainable Post-Harvest Processing of Aonla Fruit and Cinnamon Bark: A Comparative Study on Solvent Extraction and LC-MS Profiling

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Abstract

The extraction of bioactive compounds from plant materials plays a critical role in maximizing their therapeutic efficacy and commercial application. In this study, we investigated the extraction efficiencies of Aonla fruit and cinnamon bark using two solvent systems: distilled water and 80% ethanol, under maceration conditions. The results demonstrated that hydro-ethanol significantly enhanced extraction yields, achieving $25.10 \pm 0.90\%$ for Aonla fruit and $29.70 \pm 0.30\%$ for cinnamon bark. HR-LCMS (High Resolution-Liquid Chromatography Mass Spectrometry) analysis revealed the presence of functional phytochemicals in extracts, including gallic acid, quercetin, catechin, and ascorbic acid; cinnamaldehyde, cinnamic acid, and ellagic acid. Herein, we explore the underlying physicochemical factors driving this enhanced performance of hydro-ethanol, including optimal solvent polarity, improved cell-wall penetration, superior compound solubility, and accelerated extraction kinetics. By unlocking the potential of post-harvest resources for functional food and nutraceutical applications.

Keywords: Aqueous; Aonla fruit; Cinnamon bark; Extracts; Hydro-ethanol; Yield

Introduction

Natural plant extracts, especially those from *Emblica officinalis* Gaertn. (commonly known as Aonla or Indian gooseberry) and *Cinnamomum verum* (true cinnamon bark) have become promising candidates in the functional food and pharmaceutical industries due to their diverse therapeutic properties. These botanicals are rich in bioactive compounds that offer a wide range of health benefits, making them appealing alternatives to synthetic additives and drugs. Aonla fruit is particularly notable for its exceptionally high vitamin C (ascorbic acid) content, along with a strong profile of polyphenols such as gallic acid, ellagic acid, and flavonoids (Ma et al., 2024; Mehre et al., 2024; Beer et al., 2025). These compounds work synergistically to enhance their potent antioxidant activity, enabling the scavenging of free radicals, reducing oxidative stress, and potentially slowing the progression of degenerative diseases (Behrouzi, 2025; Gohari, 2025).

Cinnamon bark, in contrast, contains significant levels of cinnamaldehyde, eugenol, and other phenolic compounds (Gulcin et al., 2019; Khalisyaseen and Mohammed, 2021). These constituents exhibit antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic, and cardioprotective activities (Padmanabhan and Doss, 2025; Mnge, 2025; Elmitwalli, 2025; Jiang, 2025; Zelicha et al., 2024). Cinnamaldehyde, for instance, is known to inhibit the growth of various pathogenic bacteria and fungi, while eugenol has demonstrated effectiveness in reducing inflammation and pain (Ashfaq et al., 2024; Błaszczuk et al., 2021). Furthermore, cinnamon bark ability to modulate blood glucose levels has made it especially relevant in managing metabolic disorders such as type 2 diabetes (Zhang, 2025; Ojo, 2025; Muthukuda, 2025; Verdini, 2025). These plant-based extracts are being incorporated into functional foods, dietary supplements, and phytopharmaceuticals, gaining momentum as consumers increasingly seek natural, safe, and health-promoting ingredients (Laxmi et al., 2025; Kumar, 2025; Karami, 2025).

The extraction process plays a crucial role in harnessing these beneficial compounds from plant materials. Solvent selection is a critical factor that significantly influences both the extraction yield (Singh et al., 2023a) and the phytochemical profile of the resulting extract (Singh et al., 2023b). Ethanol is a widely used solvent due to its polarity and safety profile, making it suitable for extracting a broad range of compounds. Aqueous, while eco-friendly and cost-effective, may be less efficient in extracting less polar compounds. This study aims to compare the extraction yields of aonla fruit and cinnamon bark using aqueous and ethanolic solvents. By evaluating the efficiency of these two solvents, the research seeks to identify the optimal method for recovering active constituents from these valuable botanicals, potentially informing future extraction protocols in the functional food and pharmaceutical industries.

Materials and Methods

Materials

Aonla fruits (var. Chakiya) were collected from the local market in Thrissur, Kerala, and cinnamon bark (*Cinnamomum verum* sp.) was collected from the Department of Plantation, Spice, Aromatic and Medicinal Plants, College of Agriculture, Thrissur, Kerala. The solvent used was distilled aqueous and 80% ethanol (Food grade).

Extraction procedure

Aonla fruits were thoroughly washed, sliced, and deseeded, then dried in a cabinet tray dryer at 50 °C for 12 hours. Moisture content was monitored at 2-hour intervals and reduced to 6.30% by the end of the drying period. Cinnamon bark was shade-dried for 24 hours, with moisture levels recorded every 2 hours, ultimately reaching 9.60%. Aonla fruit and cinnamon bark were ground into fine powder (particle size 0.25 mm to 1.00 mm), followed by the ASTM standard, and sieved using a domestic grinder. Dried powder (100 g) and 80% hydro-ethanol solution (80% ethanol and 20% distilled water) are dissolved in a 1:4 ratio (Figure 1). Maceration was performed at room temperature (25 ± 2 °C) for seven days with intermittent shaking. The extract was filtered through vacuum filtration (Whatman™, Cytiva, USA). The extracts were concentrated using a vacuum rotary evaporator (BUCHI R100) at 40 °C for aonla fruit (Kumari and Khatkar, 2016) and 60 °C for cinnamon bark (Sundoro and Sulistyowati, 2022). The extract yield was calculated using the formula. Extraction yield (%) = (Weight of initial dried sample (g) / Weight of dried extract (g)) × 100

Statistical analysis

Extraction yield data were analyzed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) based on a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with thirteen replications. The Web Agri Stat Package (WASP 2.00) was employed for statistical analysis. The critical difference (CD) at the 5% significance level was calculated, and the standard error of the mean [SE(M)] was also determined.

Results and Discussion

The extraction yields obtained from aqueous and hydro-ethanol for aonla fruit and cinnamon bark are summarized in Table 1. Aqueous maceration afforded $15.20 \pm 0.40\%$ and $12.30 \pm 0.30\%$ extract yields for aonla fruit and cinnamon bark, respectively. Only polar components are dissolved in aqueous extraction because water exhibits an affinity for polar components. However, hydroethanolic extraction increased the recoveries in aonla fruit and cinnamon bark to $25.10 \pm 0.90\%$ and $29.70 \pm 0.30\%$, respectively (Table 1). This represents an improvement in yield for aonla fruit and cinnamon bark, underscoring the superior efficacy of the hydroethanolic system. This enhancement in extraction efficiency aligns with findings by Toan et al. (2021), who reported the highest yield using similar methods for *Sargassum swartzii*.

Fig. 1. Extraction of aonla fruit and cinnamon bark using the solvent maceration method

Table 1. Extraction yield of aonla fruit and cinnamon bark

Plant materials	Aqueous extraction	Hydroethanolic extraction
Aonla fruit	15.20 ± 0.40	25.10 ± 0.90
Cinnamon bark	12.30 ± 0.30	29.70 ± 0.30

The data were statistically analysed using one-way ANOVA with 13 replications. Results are expressed as mean ± standard error of the mean (SE), and significance was considered at $p < 0.05$.

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Fig. 2. HR-LCMS analysis of hydroethanolic extract of aonla fruit and cinnamon bark. 1A. gallic acid, 2B. quercetin, 2C. catechin

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Fig. 2. HR-LCMS analysis of hydroethanolic extract of aonla fruit and cinnamon bark. 2D. ascorbic acid, 2E. cinnamaldehyde, 2F. cinnamic acid, and 2G. ellagic acid.

The enhanced extraction performance of hydroethanolic extraction can be primarily attributed to optimized solvent polarity and compound solubility (Tourabi et al., 2025). With a dielectric constant of approximately 50, the hydroethanolic mixture strikes a balance between the highly polar aqueous phase ($\epsilon \approx 80$) and the less polar absolute ethanol ($\epsilon \approx 25$). This intermediate polarity simultaneously stabilizes very hydrophilic constituents, such as ascorbic acid and tannic acid derivatives in aonla fruit via the aqueous fraction, and accommodates moderately lipophilic aromatics like cinnamaldehyde and flavonoid aglycones in cinnamon bark via the ethanol fraction (Seukep, 2025). Additionally, the mixed solvent maintains a robust hydrogen-bonding network: aqueous supplies an extensive donor/acceptor framework for polyphenolic hydroxyls, while ethanol's own $-OH$ groups and ethyl moieties offer complementary acceptor sites that solvate less hydrophilic phenolics without constraining their solvation shells (Souza, 2025) These dual dielectric and hydrogen-bonding effects minimize the free-energy barrier to solute transfer and maximize

extract yield (Sun et al., 2025). Beyond solubility, cell-wall disruption and mass-transfer kinetics are markedly improved in the hydroethanolic medium. Ethanol intercalates into lipid-rich domains of the plant cell wall, solubilizing membrane components, and creating micropores that increase tissue porosity.

Simultaneously, aqueous solutions swell the polysaccharide matrix, such as cellulose, hemicellulose, and pectin, opening fissures that allow deeper solvent ingress. The reduced viscosity of the 80% ethanol blend (relative to pure aqueous) further accelerates diffusion: according to the Stokes–Einstein relationship, lower solvent viscosity raises diffusion coefficients, hastening the movement of solutes into the bulk phase and shortening equilibrium times (Kumar and Bhunia, 2025). Together, these mechanisms ensure both rapid and thorough extraction of intracellular phytochemicals. The hydroethanolic system also exhibits a powerful synergistic effect: aqueous “primes” the cell structure by swelling, after which ethanol penetrates the expanded matrix to solubilize entrapped compounds. This sequential action generates higher recoveries than either solvent alone (Aslam et al., 2020). Due to this reason, we selected hydroethanolic extraction of aonla fruit and cinnamon bark for further quantification by high resolution LC-MS. Extract of hydroethanolic of aonla fruit quantified with the highest amount of gallic acid, quercetin, catechin, and ascorbic acid; however, hydroethanolic extract of cinnamon bark was quantified with cinnamaldehyde, cinnamic acid, and ellagic acid as illustrated in Figure 2(A-G).

Conclusion

Hydroethanolic extraction demonstrated greater efficiency than aqueous extraction in terms of yield, indicating a higher recovery of bioactive compounds from both aonla fruit and cinnamon bark. Notably, cinnamon bark yielded a significantly higher extractive output compared to aonla fruit. This study also contributes to the post-harvest value addition of aonla and cinnamon bark by enhancing their potential use in functional foods and nutraceuticals. The work supports sustainable post-harvest processing and utilization strategies aligned with the goals of food security and waste minimization.

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Author Contributions

All authors contributed to the conceptualization and design of the study. Material preparation, data collection, and analysis were performed by SG. The first draft of the manuscript was written by LPS and was subsequently edited by SG. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Competing interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Ethics approval

Not applicable.

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